

THE MOVIE EXPRESSED THE TRADITIONS

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Abstract. *The article talks about the peculiarities, trends and schools of documentary cinema. Over the century-long history of Uzbek cinema, the achievements and shortcomings of documentary cinema have been scientifically analyzed on the example of films by Uzbek and Karakalpak filmmakers. In addition, the article examines the reflection of national values in documentary cinema, references to oriental exoticism, national color, customs and traditions used in cinema.*

Keywords: *film, screen, television product, national, tradition, value, documentary film.*

The development of Uzbek national cinema cannot be imagined without documentary films. Documentary film rightly expresses the present of each era and creates a chronicle of life. This is a mirror that shows today as tomorrow's history. "Simple, sometimes extremely simple pictures and film documents, which were taken once, are viewed today with great interest and excitement" [4; 6]. If you look at the catalog of documentaries, you can see repetition of themes and methods of expression. Sometimes the superiority of the characteristics of the television product is noticeable. It seems to have moved away from the scientific definitions that "film journalism follows the principles of truthfulness and increases the level of imagery" [2; 272].

In fact, film journalism, like other genres of journalism, had different principles of methodical development in different periods. Creating documentary films that reflect the national values, traditions and customs of the nation requires deep knowledge and study of the history, literature and art of the nation. While watching several documentaries created in the "Korakalpak film" studio, one can see the boundless love of Karakalpak creators for the nation and its people. Therefore, in order to create documentaries showing the basis of values, together with knowledge and experience, a high love for the Motherland is necessary. The film "Zargar" created by Karakalpak artists (author: Muratboy Nizanov, director: B. Boymirzayev) talks about jewelry, which is an elegant and unique art, in particular, about Karakalpak jewelry school and its unique aspects. There is a special approach to making a film. It shows the continuation of Karakalpak jewelry, which has been passed down through the centuries, by generations. The hero of the film speaks neither in the frame nor behind the frame. His words, his love for the craft inherited from his ancestors are reflected in the items he creates and makes.

The music chosen for the film also seems to show that the creation of jewelry is the result of painstaking and delicate work. Interviews of specialists in the field will help us fully understand the topic. Although this topic has been addressed several times and has been addressed many times in the film studio of scientific popular and documentary films of Uzbekistan, "Zargar" created by Karakalpak cinematographers is at the level of a work that beautifully shows the expression of the cultural life of the nation in a manifesting film.

The footage of Khudoibergan Devonov, who created the foundation of Uzbek cinema, is also the first foundation of Uzbek documentary cinema. "H. Devonov tried to ensure vitality in his works, first of all. That's why he didn't set his goal only to look for weddings and celebrations of various levels, and to photograph them. He thinks about observing life with the help of a camera,

recording it on tape without decorating it. From the writers we have mentioned, he learned how to accurately show everyday life and bring it to the screen with its details. Thanks to this, Kh. Devonov was able to show the hard work of the people of Khorezm who started to clean the canal with hoes, shovels and stretchers in impressive shots" [1; 17]. In addition to being an expression of our present day, a great source of illuminating history, documentary film should also interpret people's dreams, life concerns, achievements and problems.

The film "Samarkand paper" directed by J. Ishakov tells the story of the creation of Samarkand paper, which was produced in the city of Samarkand and became famous all over the world for its quality. The film shows that the creation of Samarkand paper is a very unique process. In it, the viewer will be aware of how far the development of light industry in Turan land goes back to the distant past.

The frames show the processes of connection between history and today. "If we analyze the documentary films shot in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan in the same way, although the big and small films differ from each other in terms of the subject, the approach to the views of life and the means of expression in the creative process are similar, its use, the abundance of anchor`s text, which does not match the image, but is read with pathos behind the frame, especially the empty scripts written under the influence of the infamous "non-conflict theory" [3; 17].

The success of any documentary depends on the skill of the screenwriter and director. The film "Uzbek National Costumes" shot by the director E. Abbosov is also far from social and political reality, connecting our national heritage with today, it shows that the qualities of beauty have always prevailed in the lifestyle of our people. In fact, the idea of the film is beautiful. Appealing fabric, charming colors that make people look, and dresses that glorify nationalism. The aesthetic value of the work is very high, in which the frames are further polished with the extensive use of computer graphics for the national costumes that have passed through the centuries. In a word, you can get a lot of information about the faith, dreams, culture and art of our people through the film.

In the documentary film "Cradle Wedding" directed by Lizakhan Akhimbetova, based on the screenplay of Ahmed Akhnazarov, you can see the beautiful traditions and intangible cultural heritage of Karakalpak people. The work was created based on the principles of truthfulness and imagery, the main qualities of a documentary film. The fact that the film was shot by a female director is noticeable in every frame. Behind the frame, the melody expressing the mother's mournful voice expresses the pains of femininity and motherhood. In life, the path of life, which begins with the agreement of two people, is shown as the main idea of the beauty of the so-called blessing of a child.

In the film, they get to know the long-standing historical traditions of Karakalpaks in the process of cradling a baby, their dreams, lifestyle expressions, and their noble views as a nation. In the film, the creators addressed human pasts and feelings. You will witness that the sound of the mother's song, no matter which language is played by the representatives of any nationality, shows the pure feelings of a mother. It also addresses gender issues. That's why female filmmakers can show women's lives and worries naturally, without paints. A woman understands a woman's heart more deeply and widely. It is important for a documentary to show today, the processes of our life.

The documentary film "Heritage from the distant past" was produced by I.V. in Nukus. The Karakalpak Art Museum named after Savitsky is dedicated to the history and present. Indeed, the museum you to get acquainted with unique masterpieces of art, the lifestyle of the Karakalpak people, national costumes, and jewelry. Here you can forget about existence and get acquainted with the life skills of brave Karakalpak people.

The documentary film "Heritage from the distant past" also shows the exhibits that have passed through the centuries and are kept in the museum until today. This museum is one of the masterpieces of our cultural heritage. In this documentary film, you can see the exhibits that are the expression of this valuable and priceless cultural heritage, the expression of the handicrafts that are the wealth of Karakalpak people. In fact, this documentary could have been made stronger, more expressive. The film makes good use of historical footage. However, it can be said that qualities that enrich the film, such as music and editing, are not fully used.

In the documentary film "Otov" shot by Sh. Gurbanboyev, an opinion is expressed about the values of the nation over the millennia, the oat and its related features. For Uzbeks, in general, for the peoples of many countries of Asia, the grass is a refuge, a place of feelings and the past. Every detail in yurts speaks of the peculiarities of the nation. In this film, the grass, which is an expression of the tolerant nation's vitality, lifestyle, thoughts, and material capabilities, is fully covered. If such films are translated into foreign languages and shown on the world's cinema screens, the opportunity to promote national values and traditions will expand.

In short, the artistic and life features of our cultural heritage can be found in documentaries. In today's time full of information attacks, when the world is facing spiritual crises, documentaries are important for education, spiritual worldview and recognition as a nation. In this sense, it is important and significant to refer to values in documentaries.

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